

Antibacterial mechanisms of metal nanoparticles

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Abstract

Metal nanoparticles (MNs) are the center of attention in different branches of applied sciences as they have unique features in comparison with bulk ones. They are very effective, low cost and stable antibacterial agents which resisting them requires many mutations. Metal nanoparticles first anchor to the bacterial cell wall and interact with thiol and phosphorus groups of respiratory enzymes resulting in their inactivation. These nanostructures can penetrate into the cell via various mechanisms that distort cell integrity leading to cell content leakage followed with weakening of proton motive force functioning and inhibition of ATP synthesis. After penetration, MNs implement denaturation in DNA and RNA molecular structures hinder cellular replication, transcription and translation mechanisms. Metal nanoparticles induce ROS generation which has a detrimental effect on cell viability. Beside, sum of these effects and mechanisms may lead to inhibition of bacterial cell division, cell disruption and the decline of bacterial populations.

Key word: Metal nanoparticle, antibacterial mechanism, respiratory enzymes, ATP synthesis, ROS generation, cell dye.

1. Introduction

Today particles of 1 to 100 nanometer size due to their unique physico- chemical, mechanical and electronical features have been the center of attention in a wide range of scientific fields. These tiny nanos have distinctive crystallographic surface structure and high surface to volume ratio that exhibits enhanced activity (Somasundaran P et al. 2010; Sulaiman G et al. 2013; Azam A et al. 2012). Most studied nanoparticles today include noble metals such as silver, platinum, gold and palladium that usually exhibit features different from their bulk forms (Sulaiman G et al. 2013; Wan Y et al. 2011; Besinis A et al. 2014). Silver, a heavy toxic metal, due to its chemical features and resistance to surface oxidization has a wide application in nanotechnology and nanoscale equipment (Bandarenko O et al. 2013). Silver nanoparticles with extremely high surface to volume ratio, release more silver ions having more antimicrobial

31 properties than their ions forms or compounds containing silver salts (Schacht V et al. 2013).
32 Metal oxide nanoparticles with enhanced temperature stability are composed of different
33 metals such as titanium, zinc, chromium, aluminum, ferrous and copper (Wan Y et al. 2011;
34 Vidic J et al. 2013). They can be engineered and covered by organic or inorganic compounds
35 such as citrate, cysteine, carbonate and sodium dodecyl sulfate (Ravikumar S et al. 2012).

36 Metal nanoparticles have commercial and clinical applications in biological science, drug
37 delivery and waste water treatment facilities. They are also used as antibacterial agents against
38 Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria (Somasundaran P et al. 2010). Furthermore, they
39 can be applied as catalyst and real time optical sensors (Shi X et al. 2014). Since the 19th
40 century, several compounds containing silver have been used as antimicrobial agents. In 1954
41 in the United States, silver was registered as bactericidal agent (Reidy B et al. 2013). Today
42 some silver salts and their derivatives are commercialized as antimicrobial (Sharma G et al.
43 2014) and antiviral agents such as anti HIV in early stages of viral replication (Tshukudu G et
44 al. 2010; Sironmani A and Daniel K. 2011; Akhavan O and Ghaderi E. 2009).

45 Although bacteria vary widely in shape and size, their morphology and internal structures are
46 simple, having no organelles. Physical and morphological changes in bacteria can happen in
47 parallel with the effects of nanoparticles causing bacterial cell damages (Schacht V et al. 2013;
48 Marambio J and Hoek E. 2010), dominant cell membrane distributions and the loss of
49 membrane integrity and their functions (Xie Y et al. 2011). Furthermore, membrane fractures
50 resulting from the effect of metal nanoparticles may lead to cell content leakage and the
51 collapsing of proton motive force which is necessary for ATP synthesis (Xie Y et al. 2011;
52 Burygin G et al. 2009). After the penetration of metal nanoparticles into the bacterial cell, they
53 block protein synthesis and bind to thiol and phosphorus group on DNA and RNA molecules
54 prohibiting replication and transcription and stopping cell division which causes the lowering
55 of bacterial cell populations (Lara H et al. 2010; Kim S et al. 2010; Li Wet al. 2010). In addition
56 these metal nanoparticles induce ROS generation that enhances several cell component and
57 activity disturbances (Chang Y et al. 2012).

58 Multidrug resistant bacteria (MDR) are great threat to the development of many branches of
59 medicine. Each year at least 150,000 people die of the infection by MDR strains. Therefore,
60 new strategies can be implemented to design novel antibacterial agents. In recent years as
61 bacteria become more resistant to bactericides and antimicrobial agents, the need for
62 appropriate substitutes for antibiotics seems to be very necessary (Markowsha K et al. 2013).

63 Moreover, some of these antimicrobial agents are very toxic and irritant. Therefore, most
64 researchers try to develop new antimicrobial agents which cost little and are free of resistant
65 (Kim J et al. 2007). Metal nanoparticles have several advantages such as low rate of resistance
66 mutations (Vidic j et al. 2013; Kanmami P and Lim S. 2013).

67 So far antimicrobial mechanisms of nanoparticles have remained unclear (Diaz V et al. 2011).
68 In this article we tried to present a collection of information about antibacterial mechanisms of
69 MNPs as one of the most important antimicrobial agents.

70 2. Penetration into bacterial cell

71 Bacterial surface charge has a significant effect on particles entrance. This is the first
72 interaction between nanoparticles and cell wall biomolecules which is caused by electrostatic
73 interactions (Ravikumar S et al. 2012; Diaz V et al. 2011). Probably first interactions are
74 electrostatic (Ravikumar S et al. 2012), between positive charge of nanoparticles and
75 extracellular domains of integral proteins on cell surface that carry negative charge facilitating
76 nanoparticles penetration into the cells (Schacht V et al. 2013; Diaz V et al. 2011).
77 Nanoparticles can bind to thiol and phosphorus groups of membrane proteins and membrane
78 lipids such as phospholipids (Besinis A et al. 2014). Entry of nanoparticles into bacterial cell
79 is through ion channels and protein transporters (Tran N et al. 2010). Also Nanoparticles due
80 to their small size are able to cross outer membrane pores while NPs entrance in some cases
81 would happen by endocytosis in which nanoparticles are surrounded by membrane which
82 enters the cell in the form of vesicles (Chang Y et al. 2012). Antimicrobial activity of silver
83 nanoparticles against gram negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio cholerae*,
84 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhimurium* revealed that silver nanoparticles bind
85 to cell membrane surface and disturb their functions, then penetrate into bacterial cells
86 releasing silver ions. Also some of studies focused on the antibacterial effect of nanoparticles
87 on gram positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* but no mechanism for entry is
88 understood (Lara H et al. 2010).

89 3. Effect on bacterial cell envelope

90 3.1 Bacterial cell wall

91 Cell wall surrounding the outside of bacterial cells is a very important cell component in
92 bacterial survival. Some evidences have shown that metal nanoparticles bind to cell wall

93 directly causing damage and malfunctioning (Akhavan O and Ghaderi E. 2009; Kim S et al.
94 2011). On the other hand, the first action of nanoparticles is anchoring and binding to the
95 bacterial cell wall (Ravikumar S et al. 2012). For example, silver ions released from silver
96 nanoparticles interact with sulfur containing proteins in bacterial cell wall which inactivate
97 their function (Schacht J et al. 2013). The images of bacterial cell treated with nanoparticles
98 show their accumulation on bacterial cell wall, distorting their shapes and integrity. Impaired
99 cell wall synthesis resulted from the effects of NPs, lead to the loss of essential material and
100 finally cell death (Tshukudu G et al. 2010).

101

102 3.2 Cytoplasmic membrane

103 Bacterial cytoplasmic membrane encompasses a lot of sulfate containing enzymes whose
104 interaction with metal nanoparticles inhibits their functions (Wong K and Liu X. 2010).
105 Changes in cell membrane morphology occur following enzymatic inactivation which
106 facilitates further penetration of metal ions causing bacterial disintegration through interaction
107 of MNPs with intracellular enzymes containing sulfate groups (Diaz V et al. 2011).

108 Other effects of MNPs on bacterial cytoplasmic membrane include regular or irregular pits
109 formation which facilitates nanoparticles penetration into the cells (Marambio J and Hoek E.
110 2010; Li Wet al. 2010). It is also mentioned that osmotic stress resulting from MNPs presence
111 may lead to pits formation (Li W et al. 2010; Diaz V et al. 2011). Finally, nanoparticles
112 accumulation on bacterial cell membranes induce permeability changes and collapsing proton
113 motive force (Scchacht V et al. 2013; Reidy B et al. 2013), results in the release of
114 lipopolysaccharides and membrane proteins which causes cell death (Reidy B et al. 2013;
115 Tshukudu G et al. 2010; Wong K and Liu X. 2010).

116 The TEM images of treated bacteria with MNPs showed an inhomogeneous appearance in
117 bacterial cytoplasm that probably has been the result of enhanced membrane permeability and
118 cell content leakage (Burygin G et al. 2009).

119 Potassium ions play important role in polysaccharides and proteins biosynthesis. However,
120 the effect of MNPs causes the leakage of these ions. Other low molecular weight metabolite
121 leakages are also reported. Calcium ions penetrate into cells through the opening or closing of
122 membrane channels (Raffi M et al. 2010).

123 4. Effect on bacterial nucleic acids

124 Metal nanoparticles bind to thiol and phosphorous groups of essential life molecules such
125 as DNA and some functional proteins, denature and unfold them causing dysfunctioning and
126 enzymes inactivation (Raffi M et al. 2010).

127 Interactions between nucleic acid molecules (DNA or RNA) and nanoparticles cause
128 structural disturbances which is the main antimicrobial mechanisms related to copper oxide
129 and titanium oxide nanoparticles and somehow with iron oxide nanoparticles (Karlsson H et
130 al. 2009). Ultimately cells will not be able to do replication or transcription (Ravikumar S et
131 al. 2012).

132 Silver nanoparticles cause extra damage in bacterial cell following penetrations via binding
133 to DNA, proteins and other cell component containing sulfur and phosphorus groups resulting
134 inactivation of these essential molecules (Schacht V et al. 2013; Reidy B et al. 2013). Also
135 silver nanoparticles after binding to DNA (Lara H et al. 2010), overcome the hydrogen bonds
136 which open DNA twist, denaturing, stringing or coagulating it (Li W et al. 2011). As a result,
137 scathed bacteria lose their replications ability (Akhavan O and Ghaderi E. 2009; Lara H et al.
138 2010). In addition silver ions increase mutation rate in DNA molecules therewith bacteria
139 cannot grow or replicate and the number of bacteria decrease over time (Reidy B at al. 2013),
140 subsequently eliminating bacterial population (Li W et al. 2010). Silver nanoparticles can also
141 denature and dimerize RNA molecules (Reidy B et al. 2013).

142 Gold nanoparticles also when penetrating into bacterial cell, bind to phosphorus and thiol
143 groups on DNA molecules. However, only high concentration of gold nanoparticles lead to
144 denaturation of DNA while in low concentration, DNA molecules will be trapped by
145 nanoparticles a feature which is very interesting in nanobiotechnology (Karlsson H et al. 2009).

146

147 5. Effect on protein synthesis

148 Capability of nanoparticles to interact with cellular biomolecules and molecular receptors
149 reveal that nanoparticles can reach to subcellular positions and release more metal ions
150 resulting in cell damage (Reidy B et al. 2013).

151 Nanoparticles chose different pathways after penetration into the bacterial cell (Diaz V et
152 al. 2011). Anchoring on cell surface can change cell signaling by dephosphorylating peptide
153 substrates on tyrosine residues would be a common antibacterial mechanisms of silver
154 nanoparticles (Sirnmoni A and Daniel K. 2011).

155 Other common bactericidal mechanisms of silver nanoparticles include inhibition of
156 protein synthesis in 30S subunit level, denaturation of 30S ribosomal subunit, blocking ATP
157 synthesis enzymes activity and in general the suppression of protein transcription (Lara H et
158 al. 2010).

159 Proteomic analysis shows that silver nanoparticles with 9.3nm average size accumulate in
160 proteins precursors lowering intracellular ATP levels (Reidy B et al. 2013). Also when cell
161 treated with silver nanoparticles, a decrease in amount of some proteins can be observed such
162 as glycerol phosphate dehydrogenase, recombinase A protein, ABC transport proteins, beside
163 this an increase in some other molecules such as format acetyl transferase has been reported
164 (Li W et al. 2011). Gold nanoparticles treated cells show decrease in recombinaseA expression
165 which is necessary for DNA repair and blockage of tRNA binding to ribosome subunit
166 (Murphy C et al. 2008). *S.typhimurium* treated with metal oxide nanoparticles induce frame
167 shift mutation associated with S9 fractions (Hajipour M et al. 2008).

168

169 After the penetration of copper nanoparticles into bacterial cells, copper cations are released
170 that either interact with biomolecules to form chelates which inactive them or interact with
171 active site of metalloprotein enzymes and suppress protein functions, more damageable proteins
172 are periplasmic (Chang Y et al. 2012; Varghese S et al. 2013).

173

174

175 6. Effect on biofilm formation

176 Silver nanoparticles decrease the number of cells and inhibit biofilms formation
177 (Bondarenko O et al. 2013; MarKowsha K et al. 2013; Diaz Vet al. 2011; Hajipour M et al.
178 2008), while gold nanoparticles induce biofilm formation by the accumulation of nanoparticles
179 in them (Cui Y et al. 2011).

180

181 7. Effect on other bacterial cell component

182 Flagellum detachment occurred when bacterial cells treated with gold and some other metal
183 nanoparticles. Also gold nanoparticles can enhance chemotaxis (Cui Y et al. 2011). Other
184 structural changes such as silver and sulfur electro dense formation in the form of silver ions
185 and sulfur electro dense granules have been observed in cytoplasm (Vidic J et al. 2013).

186

187 8. Effect on ATP synthesis and respiratory enzymes

188 Respiratory processes establish and maintain proton electrochemical gradient. Protons are
189 entered into the cells and ATP is made, thus proton electrochemical gradient need for ATP
190 synthesis in bacterial cells (Reidy B et al. 2013). Probably primary sites that nanoparticles
191 interact are ubiquinone oxide-reductase, silver ions interact with thiol groups on cysteine
192 residues in respiratory enzymes such as NADH dehydrogenase, cytochrome oxidase, NADH
193 succinate dehydrogenase, thiol peroxidase, glutathione reductase, lactate dehydrogenase,
194 transport proteins and proton phospholipids pumps in bacterial membrane (Vidic J et al. 2013;
195 Tshukudu G et al. 2010; Li W et al. 2011).

196 Interaction of silver ions with respiratory chain enzymes cause respiratory separation from
197 ATP synthesis and inhibit F type ATPase activity so reduce ATP level resulting in low
198 functioning of common metabolisms (MarambioJ and Hoek E. 2010). Beside these, silver ions
199 cause proton leakage collapsing membrane proton motive force activity which is necessary for
200 many intracellular metabolisms (TshukuduG et al. 2010; Murphy C. 2008). Also many
201 processes such as substrate transportation, ATP synthesis, quorum sensing and osmotic balance
202 depend on proton motive force (Diaz V et al. 2011). Malfunctioning of proton motive force
203 can have negative effect on phosphate pump system inhibiting phosphate uptake and
204 intracellular phosphate efflux which cause mannitol, succinate, glutamine and proline to pull
205 out of the bacterial cells (Marambio J and Hoek E. 2010; Li W et al. 2010). Silver nanoparticles
206 release a large number of intracellular potassium out (Kim S et al. 2011).

207

208 9. Effect on ROS generation

209 Silver nanoparticles and ions produce reactive oxygen species by various multiple
210 biochemical methods (Kim S et al. 2011). Studies revealed that silver nanoparticles disturb
211 disulfide bound, iron metabolisms and hemostasis all of which lead to the generation of ROS.
212 They catalyze oxygen reactions and generate free radicals either intracellular or extracellular
213 (Marambio J and Hoek E. 2010; Kim S et al. 2011).

214

215 MNPs can induce reactive oxygen species generation including hydroxyl radicals, various
216 anions and super oxide (Schacht V et al. 2013; Raffi M et al. 2010; Varghese S et al. 2013; Cui
217 Y et al. 2011). None of these can penetrate the cell (Xie Y et al. 2011; Karlsson H et al. 2009).
218 However, a stronger oxidizer, such as hydrogen peroxide binds to cell membrane (Xie Y et al.
219 2011), penetrating and inducing oxidative stress (Padmavathy N and Vijayaraghavan R. 2016).
220 Hydroxyl radical are a very toxic ROS and are almost able to oxidize every compounds. They
221 induce oxidative damage in cell membrane that enhances lactate dehydrogenase as indicator of
222 cell membrane damage (Chang Y et al. 2012; Karlsson H et al. 2009; Varghese S et al. 2013).
223 In cells treated with copper oxide nanoparticles a decline in glutathione reductase activity and
224 an increase in glutathion peroxidase activity were observed (Chang Y et al. 2012). Perhaps
225 high oxidative stress exchange proteins, lipids and nucleic acids later activate antioxidant
226 cellular defense system (Besinis A et al. 2014; Tran N et al. 2010). Copper oxide nanoparticles
227 not only produce ROS, but also block cellular antioxidant defense system, eventually
228 enhancing concussion. The Produced ROS have different detrimental effects such as DNA
229 breakage impressing gene expression that can induce cell death (Chang Y et al. 2012). ROS
230 bind to intracellular proteins either damage them or enhance inactivation of cell surface
231 receptors which are related to gene expression (Tran N et al. 2010; Varghese S et al. 2013).
232 ROS produce oxidative stress that damage membrane lipids and DNA molecules (Besinis A et
233 al. 2014; Wong Kand Lui X. 2010). ROS also induce membrane lipid specially unsaturated
234 phospholipid peroxidation. Silver ions inactivate useful enzymes which facilitate oxygen
235 radical uptake. ROS enhance silver ion production through silver nanoparticles interactions
236 with hydrogen peroxide. Silver nanoparticles block cell transduction in some cases and induce
237 cell lysis (Li W et al. 2011).

238

239 Unlike other metal nanoparticles, gold nanoparticles not only produce ROS, but also reduce
240 ROS scavenging ability and induce H₂O₂ and other radical accumulation, which probably
241 disturb oxidative pathway dependent on NADH and three carboxylic cycles (Murphy C et al.
242 2008).

243

244 Finally cell division stops, enlarging cells and decreasing surface to volume ratio that
245 enhances toxic substances interactions against bacteria (Ravikumar S et al. 2012).

246

247 10. Conclusion

248 Regarding to the rate of development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and their complex
249 treatment procedure and costs, metal nanoparticles could be a strong antibacterial agent due
250 their high effectiveness and low cost. Increasing knowledge about the antibacterial mechanisms
251 of metal nanoparticles may lead to development of effective and targeted new drugs. Metal
252 nanoparticles after binding to bacterial cell surface and penetrating into cell inactivate their
253 vital molecules and cause cell death then decrease bacterial population. However, today metal
254 nanoparticles are suitable choice as antibacterial agents and understanding their antibacterial
255 mechanisms can improve this effectiveness.

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258 11. References

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